

An Understanding on Education and Tribes of Tripura

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Abstract: Education is the key aspect for the development of human resources of any state. NE India is full of natural resources. The region is the land of different tribes and comprises of eight states. Tripura is the second smallest state of the region. It has achieved the status of full literate state after Mizoram by the government of India. Almost 30% people of the state are tribes belonging to 19 tribal communities. Education of all those tribes also contribute to make Tripura a fully literate state. The present paper aims to study the contribution of government for the development of the education of tribes of Tripura.

Keywords: Tribe, Education, Government of Tripura, North-eastern region, Human Resource

Introduction:

Northeast (NE) region of India comprises of eight states. The scenic and cultural beauty of the region is immense. The eight states of the region are Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Tripura, Meghalaya, Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland and Sikkim. NE India is surrounded by Bangladesh, China, Bhutan and Myanmar. It is connected with mainland India only by 22 km popularly known as Siliguri corridor. The region is full of natural resources, flora and fauna. The scenic beauty of the region makes the region centre of attraction for tourist. It is the land of different tribes. More than 150 tribal communities live in the different places of this hilly region. The culture and language of different tribes of the region are different from each other. The major ethnic communities of the region are Khasi, Rabha, Chakma, Tripuri, Hmar, Bodo, Karbi etc.

In Assam, different tribal communities like Bodo, Kachari, Mishimi, Karbi, Miri etc. live. They have their own language and culture (Assam State Portal). There are 26 major tribes such as Adi, Gali, Apatani, Tagins, Bori etc. in Arunachal Pradesh. There are 33 recognised tribes in Manipur. These include Aimol, Zou, Poumai, Anal, Angami, Kuki, Lushai etc. (Manipur State Commission for the Scheduled Tribe). Nagaland, the land of festivals has 17 recognised tribes. Angami, Ao, Chakhesang, Tikhir, Zeliang etc. tribes of Nagaland have their own cultures (State Portal, Government of Nagaland). More than 94% of the total population of Mizoram belongs to scheduled tribes. Hmar, Chakma, Mara, Paite, Pawi, Hajong etc. are the different tribes of the State. Meghalaya has different tribes like Garo, Khasi, Mikr, Jaintia etc. who

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have their different cultures. Bhutia, Lepcha, Sherpa, Tamang etc. are the different tribes of Sikkim. There are 19 recognised tribes in Tripura; Tripuri, Reang, Chakma, Mog, Noatia etc. are different tribes of Tripura.

The second smallest state of the region, Tripura, is a land of different tribal communities. The state is full of natural beauty and resources. On 1st July, 1949 the state merged with the union of India and it got statehood on 21st January 1972. There are eight districts and one Tripura Tribal Areas Autonomous District Council (TTAADC) in the state. 68% of the total land of Tripura comes under TTAADC. The state is linked with Assam and Mizoram in its north through small corridors. The state is surrounded by Bangladesh in its three sides. The state has natural gas, forest, rubber etc. But the problem of communication is the major barrier for the development of big industries in the state. Lacking in industrialisation process of the state ultimately leads to the underdevelopment and unemployment for the people of the state.

Tribe:

‘Tribe’ is group of people believed in their homogeneity and lived in a specific territorial jurisdiction. The definition given by Oxford Dictionary states that "A tribe is a group of people in a primitive or barbarous stage of development acknowledging the authority of a chief and usually regarding themselves as having a common ancestor". According to Lucy Mair Tribe is “an independent political division of a population with a common culture”. D.N. Majumdar says that tribe is “a social group with territorial affiliation, endogamous with no specialization of functions ruled by tribal officers hereditary or otherwise, united in language or dialect recognizing social distance with other tribes or castes” (Singh, Administration and Development of Tribal Community).

Tribes of Tripura:

The Scheduled Tribes (ST) of the state are viz. Bhil, Bhutia, Chaimal, Chakma, Garo, Halam, Jamatia, Khasia, Kuki, Lepcha, Lushai, Mog, Munda, Noatia, Orang, Reang, Santal, Tripuri, Uchai (Tripura State Portal).

Table1: Population of Different Tribes of Tripura as per 2011 Census

Name of the ST Community	Total Population		
	Total	M	F
All Schedule Tribes	1166813	588327	578486
Bhil	3105	1609	1496

Bhutia	28	19	9
Chaimal	549	280	269
Chakma	79813	40552	39,261
Garoo	12952	6409	6543
Halam, Bengshel, Dub, Kaipeng, Kalai, Karbong, Lengui, Mussum, Rupini, Sukuchep, Thangchep	57210	28707	28503
Jamatia	83347	41450	41897
Khasia	366	173	193
Kuki including sub-tribes	10965	5424	5541
Lepcha	157	86	71
Lushai	5384	2659	2725
Mog	37893	19086	18807
Munda, Kaur	14544	7415	7129
Noatia, Murashing	14298	7283	7015
Orang	12011	6352	5659
Reang	188220	95325	92895
Santal	2913	1514	1399
Tripura, Tripuri, Tippera	592255	298307	293948
Uchai	2447	1215	1232

Source: Office of the TRCI, Tripura

Table 1 shows that in Tripura highest number of tribes belong to Tripuri, Tippera, Tripura community; followed by Reangs, Jamatia, Chakma etc. Bhutia, Lepcha, Chaimals are lowest in numbers in Tripura. As per the census of 2011 there were eleven lakh sixty-six thousand eight hundred thirteen people of tribal community in Tripura.

Tripura, though a small state but achieved the status of fully literate state. The Chief Minister of Tripura on June 23, 2025 declared that the state is a fully literate state after Mizoram and Goa. Tribal communities of the state constitute more than 30% of the total population. Naturally, the education of the tribes in the state has contributed for the development of the state. Government of Tripura has taken up different steps for the development of educational level of the tribes of Tripura.

Table 2: Status of Literacy Among Different Tribes of Tripura

Name of the ST Community	Literate		
	Total	M	F
All Schedule Tribes	783770	431036	352734
Bhil	2240	1210	1030
Bhutia	25	17	8
Chaimal	346	189	157
Chakma	50050	28537	21513
Garoo	9716	5008	4708
Halam, Bengshel, Dub, Kaipeng, Kalai, Karbong, Lengui, Mussum, Rupini, Sukuchep, Thangchep	41904	22228	19676
Jamatia	62386	33049	29337
Khasia	212	105	107
Kuki including sub-tribes	8488	4340	4148
Lepcha	126	73	53
Lushai	4710	2342	2368
Mog	23138	12721	10417
Munda, Kaur	7837	4405	3432
Noatia, Murashing	9255	5274	3981
Orang	5256	3143	2113
Reang	109032	62559	46473
Santal	1763	1,021	742
Tripura, Tripuri, Tippera	411709	225354	186355
Uchai	1752	946	806

Source: Office of the TRCI, Tripura

Table 2 shows that as per 2011 census, 411709 Tripuri community people are literate. 109032, 62386, 50050, 23138 number of people of Reang, Jamatia, Chakma and Mog community respectively are literate. 41904 number of people of Halam etc. community are literate. Government of Tripura has adopted number of steps to increase the literacy rate of the state. In 1961 the literacy rate of the state was 20.24%. But on June 23, 2025 the Chief Minister of Tripura announced the state as fully literate state as per as declared under ULLAS-Nav Bharat Saaksharta Karyakram (New India Literacy Programme) (PIB, 2025).

As per the report of Directorate of Secondary Education, Government of Tripura in 2023-2024, there were two thousand four hundred seventy-two Junior Basic Schools, one thousand two hundred forty-six Senior Basic Schools, six hundred sixty-eight High Schools, five hundred nineteen Higher Secondary Schools. In total there were four thousand nine hundred five schools in Tripura. As per the record in the year 2023-2024 there were thirty-seven thousand two hundred forty-four teachers to impart education to six lakhs seventy-nine thousand three hundred thirty-six students (DSE, Government of Tripura).

In order to achieve the goal of making all tribal community literate the government of Tripura adopted number of policies.

Table 3: Year wise Expenditure of Boarding House Stipend

Year	Finance (Rs. in Lakh)	Physical (Number of students)
2005-2006	₹770.77	13,899
2006-2007	₹892.59	14,089
2007-2008	₹933.32	15,586
2008-2009	₹1121.25	15,940
2009-2010	₹1421.76	16,542
2010-2011	₹1532.81	20,777
2011-2012	₹1865.79	20,508
2012-2013	₹1989.796	20,564
2013-2014	₹2933.25	21,888
2014-2015	₹2683.25	21,892
2015-2016	₹3226.00	22,753
2016-2017	₹3466.58	25,070
2017-2018	₹3678.17	25,553
2018-2019	₹3605.32	25,989
2019-2020	₹4460.90	26,050
2020-2021	₹1466.30	26,481
2021-2022	₹3015.44	26,194
2022-2023	₹6027.307	29,991

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Government of Tripura

The table 3 shows that in the year 2005-06, the government spent Rs.770.77 lakh rupees for boarding house stipend. The government spent Rs. 892.59 lakh, Rs.933.32 lakh, Rs.1121.25 lakh, 1421.76 lakh, Rs.1532.81 lakh, Rs.1865.79 lakh, Rs.1989.796 lakh, Rs.2933.25 lakh, Rs. 2683.25 lakh, Rs.3226 lakh, Rs.3466.58 lakh, Rs.3678.17 lakh, Rs.3605.32 lakh, Rs.44690.90 lakh, Rs.1466.30 lakh, Rs.3015.44 lakh, Rs.6027.307 lakh for the year 2006-2007, 2007-2008,2008-2009, 2009-2010, 2010-2011, 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015, 2015-2016, 2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019, 2019-2020, 2020-2021, 2021-2022, 2022-2023 respectively. The data also shows that there was an increase in number of student beneficiaries and fund allocation since 2005-2006 to 2022-2023 financial year.

Table 4: Post-Matric Scholarship (CSS)

Year	Finance (Rs. in Lakh)	Physical (Number of students)
2005-2006	₹259.487	8802
2006-2007	₹306.332	10512
2007-2008	₹317.773	12890
2008-2009	₹433.186	15166
2009-2010	₹538.257	15649
2010-2011	₹111.40	16744
2011-2012	₹972.00	17487
2012-2013	₹1116.108	20228
2013-2014	₹1390.99	21180
2014-2015	₹974.817	24145
2015-2016	₹1437.96	20610
2016-2017	₹1155.43	19468
2017-2018	₹1725.76	14178
2018-2019	₹4078.00	22896
2019-2020	₹5095.45	22212
2020-2021	₹5517.38	26605
2021-2022	₹6116.67	35516
2022-2023	₹7010.08	37226

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Government of Tripura

Looking into the economic condition of the tribal people of Tripura, government provide financial assistance in the form of scholarship to the students. This scholarship helps students for continuance of their studies. Post-Matric Scholarship is provided to those students who completed their matriculation. There are number of students who pursue their higher studies after matriculation in the Agartala city or other cities of India. This scholarship helps those students to continue their studies. Table 4 shows that, 8802, 10512, 12890, 15166, 15649, 16744, 17487, 20228, 21180, 24145, 20610, 19468, 14178, 22896, 22212, 26605, 35516 and 37226 numbers of students received post matric scholarships for continuance of their studies in the financial year 2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009, 2009-2010, 2010-2011, 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015, 2015-2016, 2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019, 2019-2020, 2020-2021, 2021-2022, 2022-2023 respectively. There was gradual increase of financial allocation for post-matric scholarship from the year 2005-2006 to 2022-2023. It indicates, governmental initiative for increasing and continuance of enrolment of students in education.

Table 5: Supply of Free Text Books

Year	Finance (Rs. in Lakh)	Physical (Number of students)
2005-2006	₹83.48	24698
2006-2007	₹76.68	24192
2007-2008	₹105.54	28199
2008-2009	₹94.53	34452
2009-2010	₹103.98	40582
2010-2011	₹52.00	12534
2011-2012	₹54.05	16140
2012-2013	₹100.00	42870
2013-2014	₹80.00	20019
2014-2015	₹80.00	17188
2015-2016	₹70.00	21053
2016-2017	₹100.00	45313
2017-2018	₹67.50	19758
2018-2019	₹52.77	18267
2019-2020	₹80.00	22489
2020-2021	₹80.00	23811

Year	Finance (Rs. in Lakh)	Physical (Number of students)
2021-2022	₹98.67	28671
2022-2023	₹100.00	30149

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Government of Tripura

Besides, the post-matric scholarships and boarding house stipend government also provided free text books to the tribal students. The table 5 shows that Rs.83.48 lakh, Rs.76.68 lakh, Rs.105.54 lakh, Rs.94.53 lakh, Rs.103.98 lakh, Rs.52 lakh, Rs.54.05 lakh, Rs.100 lakh, Rs.80 lakh, Rs.80 lakh, Rs.70 lakh, Rs.100 lakh, Rs.67.50 lakh, Rs.52.77 lakh, Rs.80 lakh, Rs.80 lakh, Rs.98.67 lakh and Rs. 100 lakhs were spent by the government for distributing free text books to the tribal students in the financial year 2005-2006, 2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009, 2009-2010, 2010-2011, 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015, 2015-2016, 2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019, 2019-2020, 2020-2021, 2021-2022, 2022-2023 respectively.

Table 6: Coaching for Drop Out Students of Madhyamik

Year	Students Appeared in the Madhyamik Exam	Students Passed	Percentage
2005-2006	1919	1257	65.50%
2006-2007	1897	1227	64.68%
2007-2008	2378	1372	57.70%
2008-2009	2780	1214	43.67%
2009-2010	2146	0	0
2010-2011	666	0	0
2011-2012	717	503	70.15%
2012-2013	678	455	67.10%
2013-2014	689	474	68.80%
2014-2015	639	473	74.02%
2015-2016	753	521	69.19%
2016-2017	699	503	71.96%
2017-2018	648	433	66.82%

Year	Students Appeared in the Madhyamik Exam	Students Passed	Percentage
2018-2019	641	423	65.99%
2019-2020	300	300	100%
2020-2021	650	553	85.07%

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Government of Tripura

Only spending money in different schemes does not show the effectiveness of the scheme. Table 6 actually provide the effectiveness of the governmental schemes for the upliftment of the education of the tribes of Tripura. The government provides free coaching for those students who dropped out matriculation examination. Table 6 shows that 60% students have passed in the subsequent matriculation examination among those who availed coaching out of total dropped out students except 2007-2008, 2008-2009, 2009-2010 and 2010-2011. The most encouraging fact is that in the year 2019-2020 the percentage was 100% and in the year 2020-2021 it was more than 85%. Thus, those students who dropped out, again pursue their education because of the governmental scheme.

Conclusion:

Thus, there are nineteen tribes and other sub tribes in Tripura. Each tribe has their own culture even customary laws. The language of the tribes is different from each other. But, in spite of diversities, Tripura achieved the status of a fully literate state. The contribution of more than 30% tribes, among whom large section lived in TTAADC area, is immense for the educational development of the state. The government of Tripura also spent crores of rupees for the basic development like educational development of the tribes of Tripura. The result of full literacy shows the efficiency and effectiveness of governmental policies and schemes. The level of education indicates the development of human resource of any state. In this respect Tripura achieved a unique place in India. However, for complete and best use of human resource is possible through developed industrialisation which in turn required developed communication system. Government has already taken a number of steps for the combinational development of the state. With such development maximum use of human resources will be possible in near future.

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